

Development of mobile-based Fire Emergency Notification Management System using Arduino

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Abstract

Fire incidents turned out to be one of the world's generally normal damaging crises. The overall usage of phones makes it conceivable to settle on crisis decisions anywhere, even without a valid contact. This research concentrated on the development of the portability, reliability and efficiency of information and data about safety protocols regarding fire emergencies in St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA). First, a concept of connecting the SDCA community directly to the SDCA fire marshal through alert notification and responses was formulated. Then, access to evacuation maps, updated emergency plans, tips, and authorized emergency contacts was made portable and efficient through a mobile-based application. Survey evaluations were then conducted to users regarding the functionalities, portability, efficiency and reliability to analyze the data of the project. The results acquired were at satisfactory level with an overall remark of Moderately Acceptable from the users. The perceived concept for the project development of portable evacuation maps, reliable and efficient alert notification and responses was achieved through the Mobile-based Fire Emergency Notification Management System using Arduino.

Keywords: *Fire emergency alarm, alert notification and responses, evacuation plans, Arduino, mobile application.*

Introduction

When a fire breaks out the public needs a system that can help guide them to evacuate from the building in real time incidents and reach the exit safely, to reduce casualties and loses (Jiang, 2019). People spend time navigating in large-scale buildings, but it has become problematic and sometimes these people need a navigation service to reach the spots. Especially, it is relatively complex to find an exit in the building in emergency cases such as fire, gas leak, and earthquakes (Ortakçı et al., 2017). Real-time incidents face the challenge of acquiring accurate information about emergencies to respond to.

Mobile technology serves as a great prospective in obtaining information and exchanging crisis management process (Nass et al., 2018). Mobile technology offers the ability to seek help quickly during a disaster by reporting an emergency and specifying precise location through this technology. Information to public is highly important and alert notification is now able to inform large populations under immediate conditions with a variety of improved platforms like mobile devices, wireless gadgets, and social media (Sutton et al., 2019). Mobile applications profit by an expanding interest in younger generation utilizing for detailed basic circumstances (Olteanu et al., 2018). Eighty-five percent of adults with ages 18-29 years and 79 percent with ages 30 to 39 years own a mobile device with networking capabilities, such as a smart phone, most of them uses social media on their mobile phones for emergencies (Burnell & Kuther, 2016).

The main media used for emergencies is the internet and mobile devices, which is a useful and efficient way to reduce casualties; it can also improve the information spread through notifications and cope with the situation (Mockus et al., 2009). According to Hilltz and Plotnick (2013), 95% of the public uses social media platforms daily and half of the time for emergencies.

To improve communications between the St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA) community and the head of Transport and General Services a user situational response after the alert notification is available for the users to reply on and will be received by the Administrator, safety awareness and evacuation plans are also available for the users to gain additional knowledge inside the SDCA community in one mobile application with the guidance of the head of Transport and General Services that manages safety protocols of the SDCA community. Mobile application content updates are done through web application programming interface (API) safety awareness and evacuation plans are updateable, and the user situational responses are recorded and managed by the head of Transport and General Services.

Methodology

With the guidance of the System Paradigm, the levels of the System Development Cycle will be defining its stages. The proponents used the Agile method by Beck et al. (2001) and adapted by Muslihat (2018) as a basis for DMFENMS proposed project development.

Figure 1 Agile Model by Beck et al. (2001) as adapted by Muslihat (2018)

Figure 1 shows the Agile Model used by the proponents to develop the Disaster Fire Emergency Alert and Response system; this is the method that allowed the proponents to take the step by step process to develop the goals and functions of the Application.

The first level is to analyze the requirements needed, this includes, interviews, observation, surveys, and brainstorming. With this level, the researchers were able to take notes and idealize the projects theoretical capabilities and development. The researchers conducted an interview with Transport and General Services (TAGS) Department and gathered data, observed the current procedures in SDCA relating to fire emergencies and compiled research about fire incidents, mobile application, and alert notifications for the requirements needed to be included with. The project should be able to manage, monitor, and update the awareness for the safety of the SDCA community.

The second level focused on the system design and outlook; this will help with the computer hardware like the Arduino and software requirements such as Visual Studio and C#, to build the proposed project's architecture for the mobile application and web API. Design level also includes the system modules and its functions, how would it be of convenience to the project user, with this process, the built of the project is beginning to construct.

Once the development is ready, the project would be first evaluated by the expert users and then front-end users, making use of the guidance of the ISO 9126 international standard. When it comes to evaluating quality software or platforms, evaluation would be based on Functionality, Portability, Reliability, Efficiency, Usability, and Maintainability. All should qualify to an acceptable rate for system implementation, if not the researchers need to continue with the development on room for improvements from the evaluation. After the developed system would then be maintained or adjusted to fit the implementation and deployment in SDCA.

Figure 2 shows the conceptual framework of the DMFENMS, where it displays the connection of the relay to the mobile application that when triggered a direct alert notification will be sent to the mobile application through the server. The mobile application contains modules of safety guidelines that contain sub-modules of Evacuation Plans, Safety Awareness, and Emergency Contacts to be viewed by the user in any occasion. The user monitoring list is utilized to monitor the attendance and conditions of the users who responded “Safe,” “I need help,” and “Outside of school” to the direct alert notification that they received and can be viewed by the administrator along with their current information and contact number.

Figure 2 DMFENMS Conceptual Framework

Figure 3 projects the context flow of the project. The project is composed of two types of users, the administrator the manager of the accounts, and the one who raises safety awareness to the community of SDCA. The user, herein known as the professor, students, and staff, will be notified for any events and will response to safety in the situational events.

Figure 3 DMFENMS Context Flow Diagram

Level of Satisfaction of DMFENMS

To test the project, the researchers observed the functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability of the system.

Functionality refers to the system’s capabilities when performing under its purpose.

Reliability refers to the system’s maintainability, stability, and flexibility.

Usability refers to the system’s graphical user interface.

Efficiency refers to the system’s performance.

Maintainability refers to the system’s availability under enhancement.

Portability refers to the capability of the system to be used in different environment.

The proponents used the guidance of the table below to evaluate the level of satisfaction for the developed project.

Table 1 Level of satisfaction for DMFENMS

Scale	Range	Interpretation
5	4.51-5.00	Highly Acceptable
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately Acceptable
3	2.51-3.50	Acceptable
2	1.51-2.50	Needs Improvement
1	1.00-1.50	Not Acceptable

Results and Discussion

In Table 2, the respondents are the students, faculty, and staff of St. Dominic College of Asia. The system was evaluated by 50 front-end users and six (6) expert users, with a total of 56 respondents.

Table 2 Respondent distribution of the project

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
End-User	50	89.29%
Expert-User	6	10.71%
Total	56	100%

Table 3 below shows the overall response of the expert-users and end-users using the levels of satisfaction and respondent's frequency.

Table 3 Overall level of satisfaction based on respondent distribution of the project

Category	Expert-User	End-User	Variance (%)	Overall level of satisfaction	Rating
Functionality	3.03	4.22	39.27%	3.62	Moderately Acceptable
Reliability	2.99	4.07	40.37%	3.48	Acceptable
Usability	3.09	4.12	33.33%	3.61	Moderately Acceptable
Efficiency	3.20	4.07	27.19%	3.64	Moderately Acceptable
Maintainability	2.93	4.01	36.86%	3.47	Acceptable
Portability	3.06	3.90	27.46%	3.48	Acceptable
Total	3.03	4.07	34.07%	3.55	Moderately Acceptable

The system functionality secures “moderately acceptable” with an average of 3.62. The total average for the end-user is 4.22 which is “moderately acceptable”. The total average for the expert-user is 3.03 which is “acceptable”.

The reliability of the system secures “moderately acceptable” with an average of 3.48. The total average for the end-user is 4.07 which is “moderately acceptable”. The total average for the expert-user is 2.90 which is “acceptable”.

The system usability secures “moderately acceptable” with an average of 3.61. The total average for the end-user is 4.12 which is “moderately acceptable”. The total average for the expert-user is 3.09 which is “acceptable”.

The system efficiency secures “moderately acceptable” with an average of 3.64. The total average for the end-user is 4.07 which is “moderately acceptable”. The total average for the expert-user is 3.20 which is “acceptable”.

The system maintainability secures “moderately acceptable” with an average of 3.47. The total average for the end-user is 4.01 which is “moderately acceptable”. The total average for the expert-user is 2.93 which is “acceptable”.

The system portability secures “moderately acceptable” with an average of 3.48. The total average for the end-user is 3.90 which is “moderately acceptable”. The total average for the expert-user is 3.06 which is “acceptable”.

The results of overall level satisfaction of 3.55 that is considered as “moderately acceptable”. This implies that the system has a positive impact towards students, faculty, and staff. The system gives understanding for expected improvement for transparencies, correspondence plans, and administrations, and urges customers to improve truth-based dynamic for the Local Government Unit (Fabito et al., 2016).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The researchers developed a Mobile-Based Fire Emergency Notification Management System using Arduino which implements immediate response notification to SDCA community and access to portable view of evacuation maps and updated plans; with the data results of the evaluation survey the project accommodates functioning requirements and results of the reliability statistics using the Cronbach’s Alpha Test, displays the consistency of the data, proves the developed project, and meets the standard expectation of the users.

Thus, the researchers administered that the study conducted observations of current school procedures especially those relating to emergency response. In addition, an interview with TAGS was performed to better access and analyze the school’s safety protocols relating to fire emergency. Further research was compiled about fire emergencies, mobile application, alert notifications, Arduino and such. By doing so, emergency procedures and maps are portable responses from the SDCA community are dependable and efficient, details about the alert notifications are also equally reliable with the development of the system.

Several requirements were adopted in designing, such as the Arduino and routers for hardware while Visual Studio and C# were mainly used for software development of the mobile application that provides efficient and effective alert and response notification for fire emergencies.

The project was tested and evaluated by 56 SDCA respondents for the system’s efficiency, portability, and reliability through survey questionnaire guided by ISO 9126 international standard. The results of the evaluation dictates that both users concede that the system is moderately acceptable which proves that functionality requirements were met. Therefore, the project is fit for deployment and implementation.

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